

Continued Efforts to Raise Awareness About Organ Donation in the BAME Community

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Despite ongoing efforts by BIMA, there remains a substantial disparity in the rates of people opting in for organ donation between the white and BAME communities. The "Annual Report on Ethnicity Differences in Organ Donation and Transplantation 2022/2023" highlights that Opt-in registrations from ethnic minorities rose to 11.7% from 7.8% in 2019-2020, yet the numbers are still quite low compared to the population in UK. [1],[2], [3].

The British Islamic Medical Association has been working relentlessly throughout and has organized a series of nationwide community meetings and campaigns with the collaboration of Northumbria University and Northeast North Cumbria Renal network, other healthcare professionals, religious scholars, faith leaders, and transplant patients to raise awareness about the significance of organ donation from a Muslim perspective. Events have been organized at 17 different public forums since last year; including educational and religious platforms, where the process of organ donation was elaborated, attendees were informed about recent changes in organ donation laws and the common misconceptions were addressed. Patients who had received organ transplants shared their challenging experiences of being on long waiting lists. Additionally, pre- and post-event questionnaires were conducted to gather feedback.

Training sessions for Muslim scholars, distribution of informative leaflets and posters in public places like GP surgeries, grocery stores, and restaurants, and even a hike to further promote awareness were part of the campaign. Moreover, social media has also been an effective platform for raising awareness about organ donation

through initiatives like Ramadan campaign, National Organ Donation Week campaign, and the release of an Organ donation film, which gained over 4000 viewers.

Despite progress, ethnic minorities remain underrepresented due to lower family consent rates and longer waiting times. It is evident from the consensus that there is significant room for improvement in the attitudes of minority ethnic groups towards organ donation. Hence, with sustained efforts, this gap can be bridged gradually.

References

1. <https://www.odt.nhs.uk/statistics-and-reports/annual-report-on-ethnicity-differences/>
2. <https://www.jbima.com/article/lets-talk-about-organ-donation-from-a-uk-muslim-perspective/>
3. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9542453/>